

RI-VIS D4.2 Communication Strategy

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Executive Summary

With this deliverable, we want to provide a guide that helps research infrastructure managers to develop a communication strategy for their own research infrastructure. We provide recommendations for both developing and implementing a communication strategy for research infrastructures. We outline step-by-step how to draft a strategy document providing explanations on the different contents it should include such as communication aims, stakeholder analyses and the key aspects to consider when developing a targeted communication plan.

Communication Strategy

Preface

Aim and scope of this document

Research infrastructures, as service-oriented organisations, require close interaction with different stakeholders to provide services on demand, inform about their activities, engage funders etc. Strategic internal and external communication is key to achieving the objectives of any research infrastructure; however, the importance of communications is often underappreciated. We strongly recommend that all research infrastructures draft a communication strategy and allocate dedicated resources to its implementation. The aim of this document is to provide rather generic guidelines for research infrastructure managers on how to draft their own communication strategy.

This document complements the Communication Toolkit for European Research Infrastructures [1] which provides a practical set of tools, guidelines and materials (style guide, website, social media, resources) to integrate into communication strategies and activities, and we would encourage research infrastructures to consider both together when developing or reviewing their communication strategies.

As each communication strategy needs to be customised to the specific aims, structures and stakeholders of the individual organisation, it is beyond the scope of this deliverable to provide a ready-made communication strategy. Instead, this guide offers an overview and recommendations of the aspects and tools that should be considered during the process of developing and implementing a communication strategy taking into account specific structures and requirements of research infrastructures.

A communication strategy should be an evolving asset, specifically in the very dynamic field of research infrastructures with changing demands of users, funders and policy makers. Thus, regular re-evaluation of the communication strategy is key to having an effective interaction with stakeholders. You should plan for a periodic review of your communication strategy, for example on an annual basis.

In the following sections we will outline step-by-step how to build a research infrastructure communication strategy and recommended content to include.

1. Introduction

The overall aim of a communication strategy is to help an organisation to use specific tools to analyse its stakeholders and communicate with them in the most effective way with regards to the organisation's overall goals. A communication strategy needs to be supplemented with a communication plan defining specific actions and activities to achieve the aims set out in the

What is the overall mission of your organisation?

communication strategy. At the beginning of the strategy document, we recommend briefly defining the organisation and stating its mission and objectives. The mission and objectives should not be communication specific but organisation-wide, e.g., providing excellence-based access to scientific services to researchers. The higher mission of the organisation sets the framework for any communication, and all communication activities should serve the overall objectives of the organisation.

2. Aims and objectives of a communications strategy

It is important to define the aim and scope of your communication strategy and to consider an implementation timeframe. Based on your organisation's vision and its core objectives, you should outline how communication can assist in achieving these higher-level goals. It should become clear that communication aims are not just beneficial, but in fact essential, for the operational objectives of your organisation's strategy following the overall mission and advancement.

What do you want to achieve with your communication activities?

After outlining the overall goal of your communication strategy, define specific communication aims considering your desired outcome of both external and internal communications. Examples of specific communication aims of a research infrastructure often include:

- raising awareness of your organisation
- increasing understanding of the research infrastructure operations
- building commitment by the target audience to the research infrastructure goals
- strengthening internal communications to achieve acceptance and commitment to the infrastructure

With regards to the scope of the communication strategy, you may want to consider evaluating i) the stakeholders that your communication should address, ii) the messages that you want to bring across to these stakeholders, and iii) how you can bring these messages across most effectively. Based on this, you may draft dedicated communication plans.

Communication aims may be very specific for different organisations and thus we provide some general considerations that may help different organisation to develop and implement a communication strategy and plan.

3. Audiences and stakeholders

The term "stakeholder" refers to any person, group or organisation that must be taken into account by research infrastructure managers as "a party who will be affected or will affect [the organisation's] strategy" [2]. Thus, it is essential that you identify all of your

Who is your audience?

stakeholders including external stakeholder groups which in the case of research infrastructures often include research communities, policy makers, industry representatives or the public, as

well as internal stakeholder groups such as staff, board members or support/advisory groups as important stakeholders for the success of the organisation.

Analysing stakeholder groups

Describing specific characteristics and roles of each stakeholder group will be helpful for tailoring communication activities to the needs of each group. Thus, you may consider mapping stakeholders by analysing demographics, interests, needs as well as preferred communication channels. To this end, conducting a survey among different audiences may be useful. You may also want to consider potential stakeholder groups that your organisation does not yet interact with but may want to in the future.

A useful tool to analyse stakeholders and prioritise communication efforts towards specific groups is the power interest approach [3]. With this approach, you score the relative impact (power) of each stakeholder group versus their specific interest in your organisation and illustrate this in a table or plot (Figure 1: Power interest matrix method for stakeholder analysis. Individual stakeholders or groups can be plotted on these axes to prioritise communication efforts. General objective is to move stakeholders towards the right-hand side of the plot and towards the top.).

Figure 1: Power interest matrix method for stakeholder analysis. Individual stakeholders or groups can be plotted on these axes to prioritise communication efforts. General objective is to move stakeholders towards the right-hand side of the plot and towards the top.

This plot can be referred to when drafting your communication strategy and can help prioritise target audiences, especially if resources are limited. The overall aim is to increase interest in stakeholder groups with power as well as to increase the power of groups with large interest. You may want to focus your communication efforts accordingly.

In order to identify and understand your stakeholders it may also be useful to complement the power interest approach by an analysis of the environment. Specifically, tools like the PESTEL [4] or SWOT analysis [5] help to understand the environment (political, economic, social, technological, legal, environmental) context as well as the strength, weakness, threats and opportunities within an organisation's environment.

Matching stakeholders to communication goals

You should match each of your specific communication aims with the stakeholder groups to consider what you would like to achieve by communicating with each group. Once you have analysed your stakeholder groups using the tools mentioned above and you have clearly outlined your goals in relation to each stakeholder group. We recommend preparing a table. The next step is to consider the instruments that can be used to reach these goals.

What would you like to achieve in the relationship between with each stakeholder group?

4. Communication plan

Once the stakeholders are well characterised, they can be addressed in a specific way considering the overall organisation's strategy using a dedicated communication plan. Communication activities may be very specific for different organisations, depending on the relevant stakeholders, strategic goals of the organisation, available resources etc.

Key Messages

Using the table matching stakeholders to communication aims, break down each aim into a key message you would like to communicate with each stakeholder group. Consider what impression, information or impulse you would like a specific stakeholder to take home from an interaction with your organisation. Your key messages should be limited in number, clear and unambiguous and will form the basis for developing any communication content as one of the first steps of planning content should include the question of how you can best bring across your key messages.

Which key messages would you like your audiences to take home?

Communication assets

Which tools and materials can be used to address your communication goals? Consider existing material and tools developed by your organisation and others as well as material that could be newly developed. What are your organisation's current strengths in terms of communication efforts? What has been successful thus far and what hasn't worked (see also Evaluation)? Match existing materials with stakeholders and goals and consider the optimal way to make use of this material. Similarly, when developing new communication material, you should clearly define the target audience among your stakeholders and ensure alignment with your goals and strategy. What do you want to achieve with regards to this group and also how can you make that align with what they want? We recommend that you always define this before considering a specific communication activity. Consider what type of activity or which material would optimally address this goal, even if it seems difficult to implement or obtain – try to think out of the box. For instance, if the optimal way to get a message across to a specific audience is the use of photographs but your organisation does not have any stock photos at hand, consider ways to collect these – how about organising a photo competition? Or maybe partner organisations would be more than happy to share their material.

Which communication tools and materials could you use?

A particularly useful set of communication tools, guidelines and resources is provided by the Communication Toolkit for European Research Infrastructures [1], developed as part of WP5 of

the RI-VIS project. This does not replace an individual organisation’s style guide, but it provides guidelines that help to increase the individual and collective visibility of research infrastructures, by aligning key messages and improving the way different stakeholders perceive them.

Style guide

A communication strategy needs to include the development of a corporate identity as a strategic resource indicating the brand and reputation of your organisation [6]. This is typically outlined in a style guide containing a detailed description of your organisation’s corporate identity including design guidelines, examples and templates. A style guide is often used on a frequent basis as various staff members and partners may refer to it when preparing any kind of material; we thus recommend preparing (a version of) your style guide as a separate document that serves as an easy-to-access manual that you can share widely to ensure correct usage of your corporate identity.

A style guide may also include a glossary of most frequently used terms and guidelines on how to use them. In addition, your style guide may include boiler plates – pre-written text fragments that can save a lot of time later when drafting various texts and ensure that everyone within the organisation sticks to a certain language and conveys information in the optimal way. Examples of texts that could be prepared for use and adaptation in various settings include an organisation’s vision, mission statement, claim, tag line, slogan, objectives or short paragraphs with background information about the organisation. These should be written in a language appropriate for your target audiences. In addition to the texts themselves, this section should also outline how and when to use them.

Responsibility and resources

The capacity and resources of an individual organisation need to be taken into account when drafting a communication strategy and a communication plan.

Who will implement your communication strategy?

The results of the RI-VIS communication survey suggest that a majority of research infrastructures have at least one communication officer. Others share tasks among research infrastructure managers with no one fully dedicated to communications. Assigning communication tasks with clear goals and timelines will help to ensure that communications does not get pushed to the bottom of everyone’s priority list. It may also be helpful to decide upon a clear communication workflow (Figure 2) that clarifies at which stages of a specific activity feedback is required.

Figure 2: Example of a workflow of planning, drafting, publication and evaluation for key communication activities.

Which resources are available?

Outline available resources and funding opportunities. If resources for communication activities are limited, you may consider seeking

dedicated funding for specific activities.

Another consideration is the possibility to team up with partner communication channels to make use of synergies, for example research infrastructures in related domains could share communication resources and effort.

Communications channels

List all communication channels your organisation uses. These may include internal and external as well as stakeholder-specific communication channels. Consider both digital channels and analogue means of communication. If you know the preferred communication channels of your stakeholder groups, you could list channels matched to stakeholder groups in a table and prioritise channels based on your communication goals with the various groups. It is important to consider the capacity of your communication team and not to invest in too many channels, or you run the risk of spreading communication activities too thinly and not maintaining momentum e.g. on social media channels where regular posting is critical to build a following. Once you have identified communication goals, stakeholder, channels, responsibilities and resources, a communication matrix is a useful tool for developing your communication plan towards the implementation of specific activities (Table 1).

Table 1: Example of a communications activity matrix of an international research infrastructure.

Type	Channel	Primary audience(s)	Reach (individuals, local, national, international)	Inclusivity ^[1] (Excellent, very good, good, fair, poor)	Average target frequency of communication ^[2]	Immediacy ^[3] (minutes, hours, days, weeks, months)	Management	Resourcing
Internal	Email	Staff, Governance	Individuals	Excellent	When needed	Minutes	Individual	Low
	Meeting	Staff, Governance	Individuals	Excellent	When needed	Days	Local team	Moderate
	Instant messaging	Staff	Individuals	Good	When needed	Minutes	Individual	Low
	Documents	Staff, Governance	Individuals	Very good	When needed	Months	Local team	Low
Website	News item	Public, Life Science community	International	Fair	Fortnightly	Days	Editorial team	Low
	Event	Life Science community	International	Fair	Daily	Hours	Individual	Low
	Job	Life Science community	International	Fair	Daily	Hours	Individual	Low
	Science highlight	Public, Life Science community	International	Fair	Monthly	Days	Editorial team	Low
	General Content	Public	International	Good	When needed	Days	Editorial team	Low
CRM	Consent	Staff, Users	International	Very good	Monthly	Weeks	Editorial team	Low
	Legitimate interest	Staff, Users, Life Science community	International	Fair	Monthly	Weeks	Editorial team	Low
Social media	Twitter	Public, Life Science community, Students	International	Fair	Daily	Minutes	Individual	Low
	LinkedIn	Public, Life Science community, Students	International	Fair	Weekly	Minutes	Individual	Low
Audio-visuals	Videos	Public, Life Science community	International	Good	Quarterly	Days	Editorial team	High
	Webinars	Public, Life Science community	International	Good	Monthly	Days	Local team	Moderate
Meetings, events, exhibitions	Presentation	Life Science community	International	Very good	Quarterly	Months	Individual	Moderate
	Sponsored session	Life Science community	International	Very good	Quarterly	Months	Local team	High
	Booth	Life Science community	International	Very good	Biannually	Months	Local team	High
	RI-hosted Scientific conference	Life Science community	International	Very good	Biennially	Years	Local team	High
Print materials	Leaflets	Public, Life Science community	Local	Good	Biannually	Weeks	Editorial team	Moderate
	Banners	Public, Life Science community	Local	Good	When needed	Weeks	Editorial team	High
	Plaques	Public, Life Science community	Local	Good	When needed	Weeks	Editorial team	High
	Posters	Public, Life Science community	Local	Good	Annually	Weeks	Editorial team	Moderate
	Promotional material	Public, Life Science community	Local	Fair	Biannually	Weeks	Editorial team	Moderate to high

^[1] Inclusivity reflects the proportion of your primary audience(s) that can engage with the communication

^[2] How often you would aim to communicate using the indicated channel

^[3] How quickly the communication can be published from the time of its inception

Notably, the RI-VIS communication survey [7], included in Appendix 1: Summary of results of RI-VIS communication survey, has revealed that the types of communication rated as the most important by international research infrastructure managers are face-to-face interactions closely followed by email correspondence. All research infrastructures that responded to the survey have a website and most also use social media channels, with Twitter being the most popular.

As part of your communication plan, you may want to develop customised strategies for different communication channels. For a guide on how to develop a social media strategy, we recommend the Communication Toolkit for European Research Infrastructures [1].

As you update your communication strategy it is important to carefully review the selection of communication channels as the preferred channels used by different stakeholder groups may vary over time, especially in social media, and some channels or platforms may become outdated or may not perform well with regards to your overall aims.

Preferred communication channels may also adapt as a result of cultural changes requiring an adjustment of your strategy. A notable example of such a cultural shift comes as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic during which opportunities for face-to-face meetings were limited and consequently digital means of communication have become more important.

Internal Communications

In order for the overall communication strategy to be successful all members of the organization need to be on the same page. Thus, it is essential that there is a clear procedure on how the information is distributed within the organization. In other words, internal communication is a crucial part of the communication strategy.

How can you ensure the communication strategy is implemented by all parts of your organisation?

The structure of distributed research infrastructures in particular, which involves hubs, nodes and other internal stakeholder groups, adds an extra level of complexity that should be carefully considered. We recommend outlining a strategy on how to develop content, which information and content should be shared between nodes, operators (or other internal stakeholders) and the hub and who should distribute which content to external audiences. Whether there are strict hierarchies or whether each node acts independently, clear agreements are key.

Evaluation

We recommend evaluating your communication strategy on a regular basis. To assess the success of your communication efforts, consider key performance indicators (KPIs) and analytical tools.

How will you evaluate the success of your communication strategy?

In addition to measuring the quantitative reach and impact of your activities, we recommend looking at qualitative outcomes that may be more meaningful for a specific activity. For example, a social media post with lower impressions may have had a greater impact towards achieving your communication goals because it is better targeted to a key stakeholder group for example, or encourages a particular action/activity. We recommend considering ways to analyse such downstream effects rather than direct numbers of clicks, likes, shares or impressions. For example, if you are running a communication campaign to get your audience to participate in a specific event, you could include the question of how they

found out about it in the registration form of the event or if you are looking for survey participants you could include the same question at the end of the survey. In this way, you are directly measuring whether your post led to the desired action (participation in event/survey) rather than just reaching visibility/increasing interest.

Many website analytics tools also allow you to trace where visitors were coming from, i.e., whether they followed a link in a social media post or on a different website, which is another useful tool.

Identifying the relevant KPIs and their interpretation is often very specific for different research infrastructures as well as the stakeholder groups. However, KPIs provide an important measure about the effectiveness of your communication. Some helpful KPIs are summarized by the ESFRI Working Group on Monitoring of Research Infrastructure Performance [8] and by the RI-PATHS toolkit, specifically the pathway “Communication and Outreach” lists commonly used indicators for science communication in research infrastructures [9].

In this section, you could list your methods of choice for evaluating the success of your communication efforts and define time points at which the communication strategy should be reviewed.

Communication risks

In this section, list all potential risks to your communication strategy and consider how they could be dealt with. Consider potential miscommunication, misconceptions and/or misunderstandings and how to address these.

Which factors may jeopardize the success of your communication strategy?

Maybe there are certain terms that are often misunderstood or maybe there are specific themes that trigger public debate. Consider how to respond to complaints and criticism, especially on social media and plan your approach in advance.

Carrying out a SWOT analysis [5] to reflect on the strength, weakness, threats and opportunities within your organisation’s environment is not only useful for considering your stakeholders but also to identify potential risks to your communication strategy.

Finally, risks and assumptions to deliver the communications strategy may arise because of organisational issues. Is your strategy based on certain assumptions regarding funding, staff or other organisational aspects?

Potential risks within research infrastructures, especially within distributed ones, may also include a lack of identification of different nodes or sites with the research infrastructure or misunderstandings within the organisation, for example, regarding the definition of key terminology, concepts and aims. Such internal risks can be counteracted with a well drafted and implemented communication strategy.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Summary of results of RI-VIS communication survey

RI-VIS
Increasing visibility of research infrastructures

Survey on Communication Tools

Updated version
August 2020
Lisa Vincenz-Donnelly

Background

- Survey about communication activities was conducted among managers of research infrastructures from various sectors worldwide
- Objective:
 - Identify common communication platforms
 - Gain insights into strategies of international research infrastructures

Survey participants

○ 20 managers of research infrastructures

Region of activity

RI category

Digital Platforms

Information about services

Where do users of your research infrastructure find information about the services that you offer?

Media

Contact with new and existing users

Other: Phone calls, other project offering access (CORBEL iNEXT) to our infrastructure as an entry point, Vimeo

Other: Teleconferences, Vimeo

Contact with academia and industry

How important are the following platforms for the communication between your research infrastructure and academic stakeholders?

Other: Teleconferences, Vimeo

How important are the following platforms for the communication between your research infrastructure and stakeholders from industry?

Other: Teleconferences, Industry specific events, Vimeo

Contact with politicians

Other:

- Government Forums/Meetings
- Political interaction events organised by local advocates and lobbyists
- Personal phone calls
- Vimeo
- Reports

Management

How large is your communications team?

Do you use Key Performance Indicators for your communication activities?

Reach

How large is your newsletter distribution list?

How many unique visitors access your website on average per month?

KPIs

- Which KPIs do you use?/How do you evaluate the success of your communication activities?
 - No systematic evaluation of success of communication activities (5x)
 - Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube analytics (3x)
 - Website analytics (4x)
 - Number of and information about participants at events (3x)
 - Reach and reach cost (2x)
 - Newsletter performance (opening rate)
 - Regularly reporting on communication activities (2x)
 - Collecting testimonials and feedback from stakeholders (2x)
 - Approval from the European Commission (1x)
 - Number of publications, evidence of translation, patents, training and capacity building
 - KPI pending based on ESFRI recommendations
 - Analysing results of individual activities

Some emerging themes

- Face-to-face interactions clearly the most important way of communication of RIs with all stakeholders (followed by email).
- Many RIs do not use KPIs or evaluate the success of their communication activities.
 - Need for strategy on how to develop KPIs and measure success?
- Many RIs do not have dedicated staff for communications.
 - Lack of resources or rated as unimportant?
 - Need for recruitment strategies/increased visibility of RIs as employers?

Regional Differences?

- Social media:
 - EU RIs rate importance of social media higher than RIs from other regions
 - EU RIs use more social media channels in total and rate these as particularly important for communication with existing users
- Also other media seem of slightly higher importance for EU RIs in contrast to RIs from other regions:
 - Web-based catalogues, newsletter, videos, interviews

